

INDI Fresenius Kabi Research Symposium 2023 Abstract

Titles: The Role of Food for Special Medical Purposes (FSMPs) in Managing Malnutrition – A Dietitians Perspective

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Background: Malnutrition and Disease Related Malnutrition (DRM) are primarily managed by dietary fortification and micronutrient supplementation. Food for Special Medical Purposes (FSMPs) may be used when dietary changes alone are insufficient due to poor appetite or high energy needs⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. Such products include oral nutritional supplements (ONS), enteral nutrition, FSMPs for infants and foods for dysphagia^(1,5).

Aim and Objectives: This study aimed to investigate the experiences and attitudes of registered dietitians towards the effectiveness of FSMPs to treat people with malnutrition and DRM in Ireland.

Research Design: Registered dietitians were surveyed using SurveyMonkey, distributed via email, social media, Irish Nutrition and Dietetic Institute (INDI) newsletter and professional contacts. Analysis was performed using SPSS V28.

Results: Of the respondents (n=119) treat people with malnutrition and (n=111) treat people with DRM. The majority (98.4% and 99.1%) find FSMPs useful in the management of malnutrition or DRM, respectively. Older adults >65 years were reported as presenting with malnutrition (45.4%) and DRM (44.1%) most frequently. Three-quarters of dietitians (75.7%) reported that FSMPs are not affordable when not included in the Primary Care Reimbursement Service (PCRS) Scheme. Over a third (39.9%) of respondents were unaware of the safety and compositional regulations governing FSMPs^(6,7).

Conclusion: Registered dietitians in Ireland find FSMPs effective for treating people with malnutrition and DRM, particularly in the >65 year age group. Respondents view FSMPs as unaffordable when not part of the PCRS Scheme. Improving awareness surrounding FSMP regulations may be beneficial for Irish dietitians.

Word count: 244

References:

1. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). Nutrition support for adults: oral nutrition support, enteral tube feeding and parenteral nutrition. [Recommendations | Nutrition support for adults: oral nutrition support, enteral tube feeding and parenteral nutrition | Guidance | NICE](#) [Accessed 18th January 2023].
2. Health Service Executive (HSE). Prescribing Pathway for the Initiation and Renewal of Standard Oral Nutritional Supplements (ONS) for Adults Living in the Community. [prescribing pathway and list.pdf \(hse.ie\)](#) [Accessed 11th January 2023].
3. Health Service Executive (HSE). Malnutrition in Ireland. <https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/list/2/primarycare/community-funded-schemes/nutrition-supports/malnutrition-in-ireland/> [Accessed 2nd December 2022].
4. Health Service Executive (HSE). How to use Oral Nutritional Supplements. [how-to-use-oral-nutritional-supplements.pdf \(hse.ie\)](#) [Accessed 11th January 2023].
5. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Foods for Special Medical Purposes. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/press/news/151126> [Accessed 23rd January 2023].
6. Europa. Regulation (EU) No 609/2013. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32013R0609> [Accessed 18th November 2022]
7. Europa. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/128. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0128> [Accessed 18th November 2022]